

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TRANSLATION OF REALITIES IN ARTISTIC TEXT

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Annotation: This article discusses the use of realism in literary texts in linguistics, as well as the specific features of the translation of realism, the characteristics of this translation in English and Uzbek.

Key words: Linguistics, reality, artistic work, translation studies, Lison ut-tyre.

A number of studies have been made in the field of philology, including the realities of language, literature and translation studies and their translation from one language to another. Among them, Akhmanova O.S., who studied realism in linguistics and gave scientific definitions, Vazburd V.M., a Russian scientist who studied it in the field of country studies, Vereshagin and Kostomarov, who studied it from the point of view of cultural studies, Kunin A.V. is one of the interesting studies. The important book of Bulgarian scientists Vlahov, Florin S., who analyzed scientifically from the point of view of translation studies, is of particular importance. The work of V. G. Chernov, one of the Russian scientists, is noteworthy for the fact that the issue of translating realisms from the Russian language into English was thoroughly researched. The Russian scientist L.I. , and there are also certain works on the translation of realisms from Russian to French. The works of Uzbek translators G. Salomov, N. Komilov, and R. Faizullayeva have expressed a certain degree of reaction. They studied the difference of realism from other terms, thematic features of realism in languages, and problems of translation into other languages.

The word reality is derived from the Latin *realia*, which means material, real. In the dictionary of linguistic terms, it is defined as follows: "The result of material culture in existence, and in classical grammar, it is called a linguistic unit that expresses the state formation of a certain country, the history and culture of a certain nation, and the features of communication in a certain language.

In translation studies, the problems of translating realities from one language to another have been actively studied. Because this issue is addressed to one degree or another in any work devoted to translation analysis. This problem is distinguished by the fact that a lot of in-depth research has been carried out in European translation studies. In this regard, G. Salomov, R. Fayzullayeva, O. Kade, J. Munen, I. Levi, L. Barkhudarov, A. Fedorov, L. Sobolyev, and especially, as noted

above, S. Vlahov and S. Florins' books known as Non-Translation in Translation are of great importance.

The state of California in America is known for its big cities, Hollywood film town, San Francisco, Los Angeles. That's why when talking about California - meeting with California - freeway realities. Freeway is freeway in English, that is, free - free, free; way means road. More precisely, it means a road without any traffic lights. Such notes and comments are important for both the translator and his reader. Only with such explanations can we learn the essence of reality. It should also be noted that there are significant differences between the realities of American English and British English. Because even though they speak the same language, they are peoples of different conditions and mentality.

Translation methods such as transcription, transliteration, interpretation, explanation, interpretation, and the use of alternative options are effective methods of translating Uzbek realities into English. When using such methods, translators are required to pay attention to the author's purpose of using this reality instead of the context.

Until now, even English-speaking scholars have not started translating Navoi's works into English, but over time, such shortcomings have been eliminated. And finally, the immortal work of Alisher Navoi, the founder of Uzbek classical literature, "Lison ut-tayr" was directly translated from Uzbek to English for the first time. In "Lison ut-Tair" you will get acquainted with the religious and worldly issues that occupied the mind of Alisher Navoi. Every person who comes into the world should always seek to enter the path of demand, should approach his career and profession with true love, strive for enlightenment and perfection. It is an art to skillfully express a literary work in which such ever-present and eternal themes are deeply expressed in fluent English that everyone can understand.

In the work "Lison ut-Tair" the translation of the realities takes a special place. Realisms in "Lison ut-Tair" can be divided into the following groups: Translation of realisms of clothes, head, shoes.

- ❖ *Translation of profession names.*
- ❖ *Translation of Sufism terms.*
- ❖ *Translation of religious terms.*
- ❖ *Translation of names and names.*

As time changes, so do people, their lifestyles, interests, and even their clothes. In the olden days, Uzbek women wore long flowing skirts, very wide satin dresses, tilakash and ornaments on their heads, and kavush on their feet. Now wearing such clothes is not used in everyday life. Or the men wore turbans, shepherds, yakhtaks,

and socks. Currently, these clothes have been replaced by suit pants, collared shirts, and shoes. These dresses did not go out of use at all, only modern ones took their place. Without such national clothes (shepherd, hat, turban, satin shirt, nimcha, kavush) the Uzbek nation will lose its nationality!

But explaining, showing, describing or translating the names of national clothes, shoes, jewelry and hats from one language to another is a big and difficult task. This may not be a big problem for translations from closely related languages, but for distant languages it is very complicated. Because peoples are far away, language families are also different.

In addition, the way of life, culture, clothes, hats, and shoes of the Westerners are different from those of the Eastern people. So, the translator faced the problem of conveying the clothes worn by the Uzbek people who lived in the 15th century to the English reader and creating an idea about the Uzbeks in them.

In short, translation methods such as transcription, transliteration, interpretation, explanation, interpretation, and the use of alternative options are effective methods of translating Uzbek realities into English. When using such methods, translators are required to pay attention to the purpose of the author of the work in using this reality instead of the context.

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